

House Price Prediction Using Random Forest and Decision Tree Algorithms

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Abstract— Nowadays, property prices rise every year, requiring the development of a system capable of predicting future house values. People want to buy a house within their financial means, as well as market research methods. As a result, the primary goal of our research is to accurately estimate home prices while avoiding losses. When predicting home expenses, there are various elements to consider, and clients should try to anticipate efficient home prices based on their budget and preferences.

Keywords- Random Forest, Decision Tree, Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

House price prediction is an important part of home construction since it helps determine the potential worth of a property before it is built. This task can be completed more accurately and efficiently with the help of machine learning. In this research, we intend to predict house values in the context of a home building project using three common machine learning techniques Random Forest, and Decision Tree.

Many people are no longer able to purchase their perfect home due to the ongoing rise in property costs. As a result, a system that can predict future home values is becoming increasingly necessary. It is challenging to predict home prices since several factors must be taken into account, including location, square footage, the number of bedrooms, the style of property, and others.

This project's goal is to provide a system for estimating housing prices that will help clients forecast effective real estate prices based on their preferences and budget. The study employed three different regression models to forecast house prices. It is challenging for many machine learning engineers to anticipate home values. To create a model that can anticipate housing values with high accuracy and low error, several researchers have tried. The purpose of this study was to predict the sale price of a property using regression models and grouping techniques.

These models are built using parameters like location, house size in square feet, number of bedrooms, age of property, property type, etc. Regression models that were assessed for

the project, will be used to determine which computation best fits the data.

It helps people and real estate brokers in making better selections. Individuals may use it to predict efficient housing prices depending on their budget and preferences, making it simpler to buy their perfect home. Correct home price estimates may help real estate agents in pricing houses attractively and avoiding losses. Furthermore, the knowledge gained from this research can help property investors make profitable investments. In addition, house price prediction systems can help governments regulate the housing industry and avoid possible housing bubbles. As a result, the issue of home price prediction using regression models is extremely important and has huge implications in the real estate business and the larger economy.

II. HOUSE PRICE PREDICTION

A simple web-based interface that allows users to input key property parameters such as location, size, and number of bedrooms and bathrooms, and then produces an estimate of the property's value is one example of a user-friendly house price prediction tool.

For example, suppose a user inputs the features of a property located in a desirable neighborhood, with four bedrooms, three bathrooms, and a large backyard. The machine learning model generates an estimate of RS 600,000, and the user can see that the location and the number of bedrooms were the most important features in making the prediction. Once the algorithm has been trained, it can be used to classify the new, unlabeled reviews.

Overall, this example demonstrates how a user-friendly and transparent house price prediction tool can be effective in providing reliable estimates for different properties, while also helping users understand the underlying factors that influence property values.

This model will help potential buyers in choosing the features of a home that are suitable within their price range. It focuses on predicting home prices using a machine learning model and analyzing the factors that were mainly employed in the previous study to determine how much a property costs.

These models are built using parameters like location, house size in square feet, number of bedrooms, kind of property, etc. Regression models that were assessed for the project, will be used to determine which calculation best fits the data.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this conference paper, we will look at various machine learning algorithms to improve price prediction. Housing spending trends are deeply related to buyers and sellers and reflect the present economic condition. The home costs is affected by a range of elements, and the amount of space, rooms, bathrooms, and house type. A few years ago, real estate agencies estimated house prices by hand. That prediction, on the other hand, is 25% off. As a result, both buyers and sellers lose money.

Anurag Sinha [1] used a range of machine learning algorithms to estimate property prices. Ordinary Least Squares techniques are used in this investigation. The square footage of each location had a major role when deciding the price as well as the size of the area, the number of rooms, and the number of bathrooms in the home. Several metrics are used for feature extraction in this paper's scope for forecasting house prices; these variables are referred to as feature data sets. According to the findings, it had a significant impact on the placement of the residence.

Anand G.Rawooli et al [2] suggest "House Price Prediction Using a Machine Learning Model": A Literature Review. This paper focused on the prediction of housing prices using multiple linear regression and ANN. It focuses on its characteristics such as location, structure, and neighborhood. This Accurate Prediction Model assists investors and home buyers in determining the realistic value of a home.

Dinesh Kumar et al. [3] provided the following: "Prediction of Property Price and Possibility Using Machine Learning": This study examines property prediction, as well as new possibilities and machine learning methods. Using linear regression and gradient boosting, we were able to anticipate the price of a property. In conclusion, the items that the property needs affect how much a house or other property costs. The model's final projection will be utilized to provide fresh insights for future circumstances.

"House Price Prediction Using Machine Learning and Neural Networks" is presented by Abhijit Sarma et al. [4]. the method that aims to properly estimate real estate values. The system uses neural networks, linear regression, forest regression, and boosted regression. Customers will like this approach since it produces accurate findings and removes the possibility of making a bad house purchase.

1. Sifei Lu [5] suggested a "hybrid regression approach" for forecasting property values. This study uses a limited set of data and data attributes to evaluate the creative feature creation approach. Recent "Kaggle" Challenge "House Price: Advanced Regression Techniques" used the proposed method as its central kernel. The article's goal is to estimate an appropriate price for customers based on their goals and financial situation.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

House Prediction dataset is imported from GitHub, which consists of 5000 rows and 7 columns. The dataset used is in CSV format. With the help of pandas, numpy, seaborn, matplotlib, and sklearn, the dataset is analyzed. 3000 samples are taken for training dataset and 2000 samples taken for test dataset.

Data collection is the first step. Data is collected from various platforms. It contains some details for getting an estimated house price. So drop some columns from Vadodara house price Dataset. The needed columns are property type, location, size, number of bathrooms, number of balconies, total square feet of house and price.

Data analyzing based on the target value. Analyzing is based on property type, location, size, number of bathrooms, number of balconies, total square feet of house and price. The training set and testing set are the two components of the dataset. The training set is used to train the various machine learning models. The effectiveness of every machine learning model is then evaluated using the testing set.

The first stage is to preprocess the data when a user enters the relevant features. The input data is transformed into a format that algorithms can understand. To predict the house price, the preprocessed data is loaded into trained machine learning models.

```
...
import numpy as np
from flask import Flask, request, jsonify, render_template, url_for
import pickle
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

app = Flask(__name__)
app.config['SEND_FILE_MAX_AGE_DEFAULT'] = 0
standard_x = StandardScaler()
model = pickle.load(open('vadodara_house_model.pkl', 'rb'))
@app.route('/')
def home():
    return render_template('index.php')

@app.route('/predict', methods=['POST'])
def predict():
    ...
    For rendering results on HTML GUI
    ...
    int_features = [int(x) for x in request.form.values()]
    final_features = (np.array(int_features))
    standard_value = standard_x.fit_transform(final_features)
    prediction = model.predict(standard_x.transform(standard_value))
    output = round(prediction[0], 2)
    return render_template('index.php', prediction_text='Estimated House Price should be ₹ {}'.format(output))

@app.route('/predict_api', methods=['POST'])
def predict_api():
    ...
    For direct API calls through request
    ...
    data = request.get_json(force=True)
    standard_value = standard_x.fit_transform(np.array(list(data.values())))
    prediction = model.predict(standard_x.transform(standard_value))
    output = prediction[0]
    return jsonify(output)

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug=True)
```

Fig 1

Once the dataset is analyzed, we can train the machine learning models using the training dataset. After that, we can use the trained models to predict the house price based on the user input for the house type, location, size, bathroom, balcony, and area of size required.

House price estimation

House Type*:	<input type="text" value="Select House Type"/>
Location*:	<input type="text" value="Select Location"/>
Size*:	<input type="text" value="Select Size"/>
Bathroom*:	<input type="text" value="Total bathrooms"/>
Balcony*:	<input type="text" value="Total balcony"/>
Area Size*:	<input type="text" value="Total sqft."/>

*All Required

Fig 2

User information such as house type, location, size, bathrooms, balconies, and area can be used to expect house prices. Based on these requirements, machine learning models can be utilised to generate reliable price estimates.

House price estimation

House Type*:	<input type="text" value="Select House Type"/>
Location*:	<input type="text" value="Select Location"/>
Size*:	<input type="text" value="Select Size"/>
Bathroom*:	<input type="text" value="Total bathrooms"/>
Balcony*:	<input type="text" value="Total balcony"/>
Area Size*:	<input type="text" value="Total sqft."/>

*All Required

Estimated House Price should be ₹ 1820000.0

Fig 3

V. CONCLUSION

The paper " House Price Prediction Using Random Forest and Decision Tree Algorithms" explains how to estimate house prices using three different algorithms: Decision Tree, and Random Forest, each based on different features of the data. The problem is that projected expenses fluctuate based on their accuracy. To avoid this

problem, we calculate the average of these projections. As a result, it helps to prevent mistakes. This average price represents a reasonable assessment of a home's worth. Customers will be satisfied with the procedure because it will produce precise results and reduce the chance of purchasing in the incorrect location. As a major future upgrade, more features to estimate the price could be added.

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